

Thesis

Knowledge and perception of hypertension among adult in a rural community at Patiya, Chattogram

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Abstract

Background: A descriptive of cross sectional study was conducted among the adult people at Patiya Upazilla in Chattogram District. The population size was about ten thousand. A representative sample was calculated statistically and 206 respondents were included in the study. The major objective was to explore the knowledge & perception of hypertension among adult people in a selected rural area of Chattogram. This study reveals that 73.3% respondents had knowledge about symptoms of hypertension. 71.8% respondents mentioned that hypertension is related to age but most of them had no correct idea about the age group. **Method and Materials:** The cross-sectional study was conducted. The study was conducted in between July, 2021 to November, 2021. The data were collected through interviewing (face to face) of the previous listed adult Peoples. Anthropometric measurement had taken during the interview using measuring tape, Blood pressure machine and weight measuring scale. Data were analyzed by using Microsoft excel and a set of statistical techniques. **Results:** This cross sectional study was conducted among the adult people at Bara Uthan, Baralia, Bhatikan Unions of Patiya Upazilla in Chittagong District. The population size was about ten thousand. A representative sample of 206 respondents was calculated statistically. The major objective was to explore the knowledge & perception of hypertension among adult people in a selected rural area of Chattogram. 174 (84.5%) respondents mentioned that there is relationship between high BP and lifestyle but 164 (94.3%) respondents mentioned that hypertension occur in sedentary workers. 10 (5.7%) respondents mentioned that hypertension occur in physical workers. **Conclusion:** Hypertension in the rural areas of Bangladesh is increasing day by day. Now it is a public health problem in the rural areas of Bangladesh also. One out of five Bangladeshi adults have hypertension and approximately 4% of the deaths in Bangladesh occur due to complications related to hypertensive disorders. For the prevention of hypertension adequate knowledge about it is necessary to the people of the rural community.

Keywords: perception of hypertension, public health problem, rural community awareness, hypertension symptoms, age-related hypertension, lifestyle and high blood pressure, sedentary workers, physical workers, increasing hypertension prevalence, Bangladeshi adults with hypertension.

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Abstract

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Results: This cross sectional study was conducted among the adult people at Bara Uthan, Baralia, Bhatikan Unions of Patiya Upazilla in Chittagong District. The population size was about ten thousand. A representative sample of 206 respondents was calculated statistically. The major objective was to explore the knowledge & perception of hypertension among adult people in a selected rural area of Chattogram. 174 (84.5%) respondents mentioned that there is relationship between high BP and lifestyle but 164 (94.3%) respondents mentioned that hypertension occur in sedentary workers. 10 (5.7%) respondents mentioned that hypertension occur in physical workers.

Conclusion: Hypertension in the rural areas of Bangladesh is increasing day by day. Now it is a public health problem in the rural areas of Bangladesh also. One out of five Bangladeshi adults have hypertension and approximately 4% of the deaths in Bangladesh occur due to complications related to hypertensive disorders. For the prevention of hypertension adequate knowledge about it is necessary to the people of the rural community.

CHAPTER-1

1.1. INTRODUCTION

High blood pressure represents a quantitative rather than a qualitative deviation from the norm. It is a trait as opposed to a specific disease. So any definition of hypertension is arbitrary. Systemic blood pressure rises with age and the incidence of cardiovascular disease is closely related to average blood pressure at all ages. The risk associated with a given blood pressure is dependent upon the combination of risk factors in the specific individual. These include age, sex (males > females), ethnic origin (blacks whites), diet, smoking, family history, blood cholesterol, diabetes mellitus and preexisting vascular disease¹⁴.

Hypertension is a disease largely of vasculature. The pathogenesis of hypertension is likely due, in part, to functional and perhaps structural changes in blood vessels. Moreover, the primary consequences of hypertension consist of pathologic vascular changes, including accelerated atherosclerosis and hyaline and hyperplastic atherosclerosis as well as arteriosclerosis in some cases of severe hypertension.¹⁵

Hypertension may be classified as-

1. Primary (essential),
2. Secondary.

Hypertension is classified as "Primary" when the causes are generally not known. Primary or essential hypertension is the most prevalent form of hypertension (90 per cent of all cases of hypertension).

Secondary hypertension is related to some other disease process or abnormality, which is involved in causing hypertension. During the last 30 years a series of randomized controlled trials have demonstrated that antihypertensive therapy reduces the incidence of stroke and, to lesser extent, coronary artery disease. The relative benefit (approximately 30% reduction in risk of stroke) was similar in all patients groups, so the absolute benefit (total number of events prevented) of treatment is greatest in those at highest risk. For example, extrapolating from the Medical Research Council (MRC) Mild Hypertension Trial (1985), one would have to treat 566 young patients with bendrofluazide for one year to prevent one stroke; whereas in the MRC trial of anti-hypertensive treatment in the elderly (1992), one stroke was prevented for every 286 patients treated for one year.

In the light of these observations hypertension may be practically defined as the level of blood pressure at which the benefits of treatment outweigh its cost and hazards.¹⁴

1.2. BACKGROUND

Hypertension occasionally causes headache but provided that there are no complications. Most of the hypertensive patients remain asymptomatic. The diagnosis is usually made at routine examination or when a complication arises. A blood pressure check is advisable every five years in adults.¹⁴

Hypertension is an "iceberg" of disease. It became evident in the early 1970 that only about half of the hypertensive subjects in general population of most develop countries were aware of the condition, only about half of those aware of the problem were being treated and only about half of those treated were considered adequately treated. It is known as the "Rule of halves". This was the situation in countries with highly developed medical services; so in the developing countries, the proportion treated would be far too less.¹⁶

Bangladesh is one of the developing countries of the world. So it is clear that like other developing countries, many hypertensive patients are undiagnosed. It demands the presence of primary knowledge to the people of Bangladesh about hypertension.

According to WHO Scientific group the risk factors of essential hypertension may be classified as –

1. Non-modifiable risk factors,
2. Modifiable risk factors.

1. Non-modifiable risk factors

(a) Age-Usually blood pressure rises in both sexes.

(b) Genetic factors - There is considerable evidence that blood pressure levels are determined in part by genetic factor. The evidence is based on twin and family studies. The blood pressure values of monozygotic twins are usually more strongly correlated than those of zygotic twins. Family history have shown that the children of two normotensive Parents have three per cent possibility of developing hypertension, this possibility is forty- five per cent in children of two hypertensive parents.

Blood pressure among first degree adult relatives have also been noted to be statistically significant.

2. Modifiable risk factors

(a) Obesity - The greater the weight gain, the greater the risk of blood pressure. When the people with blood pressure loss weight, their blood pressure generally decreases.

(b) Salt intake - There is evidence to the effect that a high salt intake increases blood pressure proportionately. The number of hypertensive patients in Japan is high, where sodium intake is high.

(c) Saturated fat - Recent evidences suggest that saturated fat raises blood pressure. Serum cholesterol also increases blood pressure.

(d) Alcohol - There is positive association between high alcohol intake and high blood pressure. High alcohol consumption raises systolic blood pressure more than diastolic but blood pressure returns to normal with abstinence. It means alcohol induced hypertension may not be fixed.

(e) Physical activity - It has an indirect effect of hypertension by reducing body weight."

(f) Environmental stress - Hypertension is initiated by tension or stress. The over activity of sympathetic nervous system has an important part to play in the pathogenesis of hypertension.

(g) Other factors - Oral contraceptive is a risk factor for hypertension.¹⁶ Community can positively influence modifiable risk factors of hypertension if they have knowledge about the risk factors of hypertension. We know that the only thing more expensive than education is ignorance. So knowledge about hypertension in community is needed to prevent it. Now-a-days hypertension is also significantly found in the rural area of Bangladesh.

In a study in a rural area of Bangladesh, a total of 5,026 persons were examined. The largest number of cases was in the age group 20-29 (1,544 cases) and 30 to 39 years (1,089 cases). Total number of females Was 2,400 (47.75) of which 300 (12.5%) were in age group of 30:39 years. A total of 337 cases were detected to have elevated blood pressure. The range of diastolic blood pressure was found 90to94 mm Hg in 198 (cases, 95 to 104 mm Hg in 96 cases, 105-to1 14 mm Hg in 36 cases, 115+ mm Hg in 7 cases⁴.

The Village selected for the survey was Seven kilometer away from the city of Chattogram. In an earlier study Islam et. al. (1979) found 13.6% of 7972secretariate population to have elevated blood pressure. This population represents urban population to Chattogram city. In the next study in the rural area, 6.7% of population was found to have elevated blood pressure. It indicates that hypertension is less frequently present in rural population than urban population. The public and the profession should be made aware that timely control of hypertension prevents cardiovascular, cerebrovascular and renal complications.¹⁷ The situation of rural area of Bangladesh is rapidly changing. The changes are in the life style, industrialization, urbanization etc; that cause increase risk of hypertension among the rural people of Bangladesh. For this reason it is essential to estimate the knowledge about hypertension in the rural people of Bangladesh.

1.3 JUSTIFICATION

In Bangladesh, hypertension is one of the major non-communicable diseases. The researcher worked in some of the rural areas of Bangladesh as Medical Officer for about three years. In that time it was found that a significant number of people of the rural areas are hypertensive. Most of the hypertensive patients of the rural areas are unaware about their hypertension. As most of the patients remain asymptomatic, the asymptomatic patients are unaware about it. Thus hypertension silently increases morbidity and mortality especially in the rural areas of Bangladesh. Hypertension occasionally causes headache but provided there are no complications, most patients remain asymptomatic. Accordingly, the diagnosis is usually made at routine examination or when a complication arises. A blood pressure check is advisable in every five years in adults but the people of rural areas of Bangladesh are not aware about it. So the researcher chose the present topic.

There are many probable causes of increase rate of hypertension in rural community of Bangladesh. Changing the life style is seen in the rural area. Electricity supply causes prevention of early-night sleep; T.V, Video etc have rapidly spread in rural area.

Previously only one crop was produced in a field in a year, and then crisis of food was a major problem in rural area. Now by the development of agricultural science more than one crop is produced in a field in a year. So crisis of food is reduced and thus life style is changed, some of the people of rural area are introduced into sedentary life style because of better economy.

Food habit is also changed in the rural area. Alcoholism and other addictions are increased in the rural area, which are the risk factors of hypertension. To control hypertension in the rural area of Bangladesh, a plan is required.

For this purpose, it is necessary to estimate the knowledge of the people in the rural area about hypertension. Previous study about knowledge of the people about hypertension is not found. So the present research topic is the knowledge & perception of hypertension among adult people in a rural community of Bangladesh.

1.4. RESEARCH QUESTION

What is the level of knowledge & perception of hypertension among adult people in a rural community of Bangladesh?

1.5. OBJECTIVE

General objective: To find out the knowledge & perception of hypertension among adult people in a rural community at Patiya, Chattogram.

Specific objectives

1. To explore the knowledge & perception of the respondents regarding hypertension.
2. To explore the knowledge of the respondents about risk factors of hypertension eg, age, sex, dietary habit (extra salt intake, saturated fat intake), sedentary life style, mental stress, family history of hypertension, relation of hypertension with diabetes.
3. To find out the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents.
4. To find out the level of knowledge of the respondents regarding preventive measures of hypertension.

1.6. LIST OF VARIABLES:

Key variables

- i) Knowledge (regarding risk factors of hypertension)
 - a) Smoking
 - b) Dietary habit
 - c) Obesity
 - d) Life style
 - e) Mental stress
- ii) Awareness (regarding consequences of hypertension)
 - a) Coma
 - b) Paralysis
 - c) Speech disturbance
 - d) Ventricular hypertrophy
 - e) Heart failure
 - f) Cerebral hemorrhage
 - g) Disturbance of vision
 - h) Ischaemic Heart Disease
- ii) Sociodemographic characteristics
 - a) Age of the respondents
 - b) Gender of the respondents
 - c) Marital status
 - d) Religion
 - e) Occupation
 - f) Educational status
 - g) Monthly income

1.7. OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF VARIABLES

Knowledge: In this study in case of correct answer of a question, given by the respondents is considered as knowledgeable. In case of multiple correct answers of a question, more than one correct answer given by the respondents is considered as knowledgeable. Dietary habit: Pattern of consumption of different types of food related to hypertension eg. fat, protein, extra. salt.

Obesity: Physical appearance of any person which indicates overweight by naked eye inspection.

Life style: In this study it indicates types of activities by any person, one is physical activity eg works of farmers, day-labourers and another is mental activity. eg, works of service holders, businessman.

Mental stress: conditions eg. tension, excitation, depression which cause psychological stress.

CHAPTER- 2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Possible searching of literature was done but study regarding knowledge about causes and consequences of hypertension among the adult people is not found although many studies about hypertension are present. Some of the literatures are reviewed here.

In the light of these observations hypertension may be practically defined as the level of blood pressure at which the benefits of treatment outweigh its cost and hazards.¹⁴

Hypertension occasionally causes headache but provided that there are no complications. Most of the hypertensive patients remain asymptomatic. The diagnosis is usually made at routine examination or when a complication arises. A blood pressure check is advisable every five years in adults.¹⁴

In Bangladesh prevalence of hypertension ranges from 12% to 19.6% in different selected population. In hospital population hypertension attributes to 70% of strokes, 23.8% Myocardial Infarction and 11% renal failure. Prevention of essential hypertension is possible by undertaking modification of life cycle. Though genetic factors play a great role in the causation of hypertension, the modification of environmental factors with alteration of life style has shown beneficial effect on hypertension.¹

Haque MS, Ali SMK, A Wiz's² study on an exercise training combined with dietary program for patients with hypertension reveals that there was a moderate degree of positive correlation between decrease in body weight and systolic blood pressure in hypertensive group. The study was carried out in 1992-1993 at the Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Dhaka. Only male subjects referred to the outpatient department of the hospital for treating hypertension were previously included in the study. The presence of hypertension was established following WHO 1984 criteria. i.e. by taking three measurements on each of at least two different occasions. Patients taking antihypertensive drugs, those with secondary hypertension and with cardiovascular or neurological complications were excluded from the study. Twenty-eight hypertensive subjects with diastolic blood pressure in the range of 85 to 90 mm Hg (high normal

blood pressure) were eventually included in the study. All of them were admitted in CMCH. On the day of admission height, weight, routine urine and blood analysis, ECG and X-ray chest examination were carried out. BP was recorded in sitting position with the help of mercury sphygmomanometer. All measures were taken by a trained Medical Assistant at different times of the day. The data were recorded in a standard data collection proforma. A four weeks screening period was followed by the clinical trial. All the subjects had to follow a controlled exercise program comprising brisk and sustained walking on a treadmill set with progressive increase or decrease in time. The subject had to consume a diet containing less than 2.5 gm common salt per day. The energy intake was limited to 2000 KCal per day. 24 % of total energy intake was given in the form of unsaturated and 6% as saturated fat. All food-stuffs were weighed before cooking and the left over amount were measured and subtracted to maintain correct food consumption. The quality control checks were carried out throughout the study. The result was weight loss ranges from 1 to 3 kg in the hypertensive and 1 to 2 kg in the non-hypertensive groups. The mean weight loss was 1.66 kg and 1.5 kg respectively in the two groups. The correlation between systolic blood pressure and body weight reduction in normotensive group was insignificant ($r=0.06$). A moderate degree of positive correlation was noted ($r= 0.302$) between decrease in body weight and systolic blood pressure in the hypertensive group.

A study was conducted upon a serial changes in blood pressure from childhood into young adulthood for females in relation to body mass index and maturation age by Shumei Guo, Eric Chi, Wayne Wisemandle and associates³. One important area of investigation is the study of relationships of adulthood blood pressure values to earlier childhood blood pressure values in the same individuals. Such a relationship is referred to as tracking. When an aberrant BP level is found in childhood, the extent to which it should be regarded as a guide to future BP values in adulthood depends on the extent of tracking. If BP values track, then early intervention to prevent subsequent aberrant levels in adulthood should be considered. Tracking in this context is defined as the occurrence of positive correlation coefficients between repeated measures of BP in the same individuals at different ages, or points in time. Studies of tracking in BP during childhood and adolescence were also summarized that in some studies the correlation were low and thus the implication of childhood BP values, as predictors of adult values was unclear. In most studies, the length of follow-up did not

extend from childhood to adulthood, and the length of follow-up was extremely variable from study to study. In the results were arranged into seven mutually exclusive age ranges: 8-10, 10-12, 12-14, 14-16, 16-18, 18-20 and 20-22. If an individual had more than one measurement within these groups, the first measurement was used. Mean and standard deviations for systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP), the body mass index, and maturational age status are measured. The females attained menarche between 12 and 14 years of age with a standard deviation at 1 year. The means for the BMI increased from 16.45 kg/m² at 8- 10 years to 22.23kg/m² at 20- 22 years. The means for SBP increased from 90.35 mm Hg at age 8-10 years to 105.1 mm Hg at age 20-22 years. The DBP values increased from 55.67 mm Hg at 8-10 years to 64.55 mm Hg at 20-22 years. BP models were significantly improved when the BMI deviations were induced (SBP: Chi-square statistic 504, d.f.-1, P is lesser than 0.01; DBP: Chi-square statistic = 508, d.f. =1,

P is lesser than 0.01) indicating that there were significant effects of an elevated BMI on increased BP values from 8-22 years. From the analysis, the following conclusions are indicated:

- a) At the same chronological age, early maturing females had significantly greater BMI values than the late maturing females.
- b) An average increase of 1kg/m² in deviation from the population means of the BMI resulted in an average increase of 1.2 mm Hg/year in SBP and of 0.6 mm Hg/year in DBP.
- c) Significant tracking exists for BMI. Tracking is moderate for SBP and DBP. This tracking is inversely related to the length of time intervals between measurements.

A study on 'Blood Pressure and Adiposity: A Comparative Study of Socioeconomically Diverse Groups of Andhra Pradesh, India' was conducted by B. Nirmala Reddy.⁴ Height, weight, four skinfold thicknesses (triceps, biceps, subscapular and suprailiac) and systolic (SBP), and diastolic (DBP) blood pressures of 1119 subjects, 456 males and 663 females, 18 to 75 years age were measured. Information on habitual physical activity, smoking, food habits, and income were also obtained. The sample was divided into four groups (I, II, III and IV). The sample size, occupation, average social ranking, average economic grade, physical activity level, food habit, habitat, Relative literacy grade of Group 1,11,111,IV were 156, seminomadicartisans, 3, 4, heavy, non veg, rural, very low,409, agricultural labour, 4,

3, heavy, non veg, semi-rural, low; 318, landholding agriculturists and petty trades, 2, 2, medium, non veg, semi-rural, medium; 236, service and business, 1, 1. light, veg, urban, high respectively. No systematic sampling design was used in drawing the samples although care was taken not to include related subjects. The BP were taken using an Astropulse 78 Digital Electronic bp. Essential hypertensives were classified according to the diagnostic criteria of the WHO (1959). The subjects were classified as hypertensive when they had SBP ≥ 160 mm Hg and/ or DBP ≥ 95 mm Hg. Individuals with SBP between 141 and 159 mm Hg were classified as borderline hypertensive. The remaining subjects were classified as normotensive. Height and weight were measured using standard anthropometric instruments and procedures. Skin-fold thickness were measured on the left side at four sites triceps, biceps, subscapular, suprailiac, using a large caliper. Statistical analysis was done by using the Binominal Data Processing (BMDP) software and the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSSX). Group and sex-specific descriptive statistics of blood pressure and adiposity were first calculated. Inter-group differences were evaluated with analysis of variance (ANOVA). Significant differences between age groups, sexes and populations were found. However significant population-sex and age-sex interactions were found only for SBP, Not for DBP. Further analysis was performed separately for each group and sex. Results eg. means and standard deviations of SBP and DBP and the prevalence of hypertension were measured. There is a clear increase in mean blood pressures and in the incidence of hypertensives from the seminomadic Yerukalas (group I) to the urbanized population (group IV), especially in males. The most affluent population of group IV has the largest proportion of hypertensives (7.8% in males and 4.8% in females) and the traditional seminomadic Yerukalas the lowest proportion (0.0%). This trend is more clear in case of borderline hypertensives or when both types are pooled. The seminomadic Yerukala tribe does not show any hypertensive individuals, males or females, and only two males and one female are in the borderline category. These results suggests a positive association between the proportions of hypertensives, borderline hypertensives, and normotensives in a population and the socioeconomic ranking (Chi-square 22.6 and 17.4, for males and females with 6 d.f., $p < 0.01$), Age-related differences in mean blood pressures are either not consistent or very insignificant in case of the Yerukala tribe and among the physically active Mala and Muslim populations of group II, especially males, while there is a progressively increasing trend of mean SBP with age among the latter two

groups. The latter trend is particularly steep in females. However, females of group II also show a higher mean SBP in the older age groups. On the other hand, DBP shows a consistent increase to about 50 years of age, followed by a gradual decline (an inverted U-shaped), especially in groups III and IV, the socioeconomically more advanced groups who perform very little physical activity. This may be due, in part, to a cohort effect, since this is a cross-sectional study: older adults in these groups may have experienced the lifestyle changes and modernization to a lesser degree, and thus have lower blood pressure. Mean DBP is almost invariably over age groups in the less privileged and socioeconomically depressed populations in group II and among the seminomadic Yerukalas. Results of the ANOVAS suggest significant ($p \leq 0.01$) heterogeneity of mean SBP over age groups in the affluent groups III and IV but not among the traditional Yerukalas and hard working group II. Correlation between adiposity and blood pressures reflects not only the association between pairs of variables, not the cause-effect relationships. This analysis was done on the pooled sample, using one factor at a time, because within certain groups not all levels of the categorical variables were present. Each of five factors (physical activity, smoking, income, food habit and group affiliation) explain significant amounts of residual variation (after adjusting for covariates) in SBP ($p = 0.042$, for smoking; for the others, $p = 0.000$) among males. In the pooled sample of females, out of the four factors (smoking is excluded because all females are nonsmokers), only food habit ($p = 0.028$) and group affiliation ($p = 0.002$) show significant = effect on the residual variance of SBP. The relationship of group affiliation with SBP is not, however, as clear since group III, not group I, has the lowest mean. Only physical activity, income and group affiliation explain a significant amount of residual variation ($p < 0.001$) in DBP among males but none of the four categorical variables do so in females. Although group affiliation is significant in males, the relationship is not clear; there is a trend for an increase in mean DBP with an increase in SES from groups II to IV but group I distorts the trend by showing the highest DBP. Heavy physical activity is associated with reduced mean blood pressures, suggesting negative relationship; vegetarianism is associated with higher mean SBP. On the other hand, smoking, higher social status is each associated with increased mean SBP. DBP and categorical variables are qualitatively similar, except in the traditional Yerukalas. Since the lifestyle variables are related, ANCOVA was done using four of the five factors, simultaneously. Population and food habit could not be used simultaneously due to

the resulting singular matrix. Within each of the populations, food habit is constant; members of populations I to III are non-vegetarians which those of population IV are vegetarians. Therefore food habit was excluded. The results suggest that only physical activity $F= 12.4$, $p = 0.00$) and smoking ($F = 15.4$, $p = 0.00$) are significant, although when analyzed independently each of the five factors explained a significant amount of variation in SBP in males. In females only group membership is significant ($F= 6.55$, $p = 0.00$). Physical activity type is strongly correlated to income and group/social status; hence, the latter make no further contribution. Income ($F = 3.4$, $p = 0.034$) and group membership ($F = 5.31$, $p = 0.001$) make significant contribution to DBP in males, but none of the categorical variables do so in females. The present study shows a consistent relation among adiposity, other risk factors and blood pressure. This relationship is strongest in most affluent groups, and in men than in women. In men adiposity, fat patterning, physical activity and age make significant contribution to variation in blood pressures, while in the women, age appears to be strongest predictor of blood pressure variation. Thus, factors associated with an urban lifestyle more strongly influence with an urban lifestyle more strongly influence blood pressure in men than in women.

Toselli S, Graziani I, Taraborelli T, Grispan A, Tarsitani G and Gruppioni's⁵ study on body composition and blood pressure in school children 6-14 years of age reveals that the BMI increases regularly from 6-14 years in both sexes from 17.4-22.9 kg/m² in females and 17.2-21.7 kg/m² in males. The values are generally similar in both sexes, with the largest difference occurring at 14 years. Females have larger skinfold thicknesses than males, especially at the triceps where the difference is significant for all age classes except 8 and 10 years.

A study was conducted by A. Roberto Frisancho, S. Farrow, Isabel Friedenzohn⁶ et. al. regarding the role of genetic and environmental factors in the increased blood pressure of Bolivian Blacks. As noted earlier, there is no differences between blacks and nonblacks in the number of people who speak Spanish, but a significantly greater number of nonblacks speak Aymara as described by Woodillin 1996. About 84% of Chicaloma subjects own their house, 83% have access to electricity, 26% own registrations, and 55% own a television set. Further, a significantly greater percentage of blacks own their house (87.8% for blacks and 79.1% for nonblacks). Moreover, a

significantly greater percentage of blacks have access to electricity (88.9% for blacks and 76.1% for nonblacks), own a refrigerator (28.9% of blacks and 20.9% of nonblacks) own a television set (63.3% of blacks and 43.3% for nonblacks). Overall, blacks have a higher economic status than nonblack samples. To investigate the relationship between socioeconomic status and blood pressures, an ownership index (OI) was calculated. The index is based on population reciprocals for the frequencies of (1) home ownership, (2) access to electricity, (3) possession of a television set, and

(4) possession of a refrigerator. For example, the OI for house ownership in the population as a whole would equal 1.19 ($1/84.1 \times 100 = 1.19$), 1.20 for access to electricity ($1/83.4 \times 100 = 1.20$), 3.92 for ownership of refrigerator ($1/25.5 \times 100 = 3.92$), and 1.82 for ownership of a television set ($1/54.8 \times 100 = 1.82$). In this manner, each household was accorded an OI depending on whether or not it owned its home, had access to electricity, owned a television set and refrigerator. The use of reciprocals gave the greatest weighting to the least frequently owned of these four amenities. Results of this analysis indicate that blacks have a higher OI than non-blacks. In terms of body size and composition, blacks are significantly taller and heavier and have a great mid upper arm muscle area and higher lean body mass than non-blacks. The prevalence of hypertension is higher for blacks (7.9% for systolic and 5.9% for diastolic blood pressures) than non-blacks (1.3%). Genetic studies among blacks from the islands of Barbados and La Desirade indicate that individuals having the largest proportion of African mitochondrial DNA have a higher mean systolic blood pressure and higher hypertension prevalence than those of non-African lineage.

Chery Smith⁷ conducted a study on blood pressure on Serpa men in modernized Nepal. No significant difference was found between LAS (Low Altitude Sample) and HAS (High Altitude Sample) for SBP; however, the HAS sample had significantly higher DBP. LAS men were significantly shorter and had higher mean BMIs and triceps and subscapular skinfolds. The leanest men were found among the rural HAS sample; compared to the urban HAS sample, they had significantly lower mean weights, BMIs, and triceps and subscapular skinfolds, and expended the most energy. The men living in Kathmandu expended the least amount of energy, falling into the 'light activity' category by WHO standards; the rural HAS men expended the highest amount of energy, falling into the moderate to high activity' category. Distribution of normotensive (SBP < 140 and/or DBP < 90) and elevated BPs are also recorded. The 59

men with elevated BPs included 23 hypertensives (BP \geq 160/95, LAS: 12 men and HAS: 11 men). Stepwise regression analysis showed that the BMI, age, and alcohol consumption were strong predictors for SBP, and the BMI and age were strong predictors for DBP in the total sample of men with normal and elevated BPs. However, when the stepwise regression analysis were run for each group separately, the BMI and alcohol were strong predictors for SBP, and the BMI, age and alcohol were strong predictors for DBP in the urban HAS. Men with elevated BPs had higher mean weight, BMI, and subscapular and triceps skinfolds. Men with elevated BPs consumed more alcohol, and those with elevated SBP consumed more alcohol.

A study was conducted by Ping An, Treva Rice, Jacques Gagnon⁸ et. al. about cross- trial familial resemblance for resting blood pressure and body composition and fat distribution: the heritage family study. Coefficient of variations (CV) for repeated measures were 4% and 6% for resting SBP and DBP, respectively. The intraclass correlations (ICCS) for repeated measures are 0.84 and 0.79 for resting SBP and DBP, respectively. Reproducibility of anthropometric and body composition and fat distribution measures is very high, ranging from 0.95 to 1.00. Means and SDs of the unadjusted resting variables were presented. In the both generations, there were no sex differences in the means for age and FM (Fat Mass). FFM (Fat-Free Mass), TER (Trunk to Extremity skinfolds), WAIST (Waist circumference), and WHR (Waist to Hip circumference) were greater in males, whereas, %BF (Percent Body Fat), SF (Skin Fold), and TAF (Total Abdominal Fat) were higher in females. In both sexes, parents tended to have higher BP and body composition and fat distribution measures than offspring, except no significant differences in SBP and FFM were noted for fathers vs. sons, and in TER for mothers vs. daughters. In general, age accounts for little to moderate variance (ranging from zero to 25%), with more variance accounted for in offspring (especially sons) than in parents. As expected, FM accounted for an appreciable percentage of the variance in AVFf (from 43% in fathers to 76.2% in sons, $P < 0.05$), in TAF (from 85.3% in fathers to 94.4% in sons $P < 0.05$), in WAISTE (from 69.7% in mothers to 90.9% in sons, $P < 0.05$), and in WHRf (from 20.7% in mothers to 75.2% in sons, $P < 0.05$), although relatively little was accounted for in TERf (zero to less than 10%, $P < 0.05$). The intraindividual cross-trait correlations among %BF, AVF, BMI, FM, SF, TAF, and WAIST are generally high (0.58-0.97), except 0.37 for AVF- SF in fathers. WHR and the remaining variables are

significantly correlated (0.20-0.90), except for a nonsignificant intraindividual correlation with TER in fathers. Correlations of FFM with the remaining variables except TER range from 0.17 to 0.72, or are nonsignificant with %BF, WRH in mothers. Correlations of TER with the remaining variables are nonsignificant in mothers and offspring.

William W. Dressler, Mauro C. Baliero and Jose Ernesto Dos Santos" study on culture, skin colour, and arterial blood pressure in Brazil reveals that darker skinned Brazilians have higher blood pressures than light skinned Brazilians only if they have low cultural consonance in lifestyle.

Marshall Smith Mim and Takusei Umenai Md's study¹⁰ was conducted upon knowledge, attitude and practice of smoking among University students of allied health sciences in Japan. It was a cross-sectional comparative study developed in line with WHO's was recommended core questions for assessing smoking status. Ever smokers were defined as having smoked at least one cigarette in their life time and nonsmokers were defined as never having touched tobacco; ever-smokers who had smoked less than 100 cigarettes and those who had smoked 100 or more; and finally current smokers and ex-smokers. The significant differences were most notable in the first comparison of ever-smokers and nonsmokers. Among the 356 subjects interviewed, 18.3% were ever-smokers. 34.2% of male students and 14.5% of female students had ever smoked. Although the scale of the study was limited, significant preliminary results had become evident concerning several fundamental smoking and tobacco control issues. Students' knowledge, attitudes and practice towards those were also measured.

Obese adults have shown increased left ventricular mass, left ventricular wall thickness, and left ventricular cavity size compared with that of lean subjects. One important mechanism may be related to the increased circulatory blood volume of obesity, secondary to sodium and water retention. As a consequence, cardiac output increases because of an increase in stroke volume. Obesity, particularly with a pattern of abdominal fat distribution, may be viewed as the clinical evidence of multiple metabolic alterations that are either clinically overt e.g. type 2 diabetes, hypertension.¹¹

CHAPTER- 3 METHODOLOGY

3.1. Type of study

This is a descriptive type of cross-sectional study conducted among the adult population in a rural community at Patiya, Chattogram

3.2 Time of study

The study was conducted from July 2021 to November 2021 Duration of study was Five months.

3.3 Study population

Adult population of 3 selected union (Bara Uthan, Baralia & Bhatikhan) at Patiya Upazilla, Chattogram.

3.4 Place of study

The study was carried out at Bara Uthan, Baralia & Bhatikhan Union of Patiya Upazilla in Chittagong District.

3.5. Sample size- Sample size was determined by using suitable statistical formula. The sample size formula is

$$= \frac{Z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

Z (=1.96) is the value from the normal distribution that cuts off 2.5% in either tail (or include the middle 95% of the distribution) Where p is expected value of the proportion, q=1-p. d is the required precision.

Estimated minimum sample size = 384

Where Z=1.96

$$p=0.50$$

$$d=0.05$$

But for practical purpose (due to limitation of time and logistic support) the sample size was calculated by increasing the precision from 0.05 to 0.07. So calculated sample size was 206.

3.6. Sampling technique: Non probability type

3.7. Data collection instrument: A structured questionnaire was developed in the light of the objectives. The questionnaire was finalized by modifying after pre- test.

3.8. Data collection procedure

For the collection of relevant data one method was followed.

Interviewing-

Prior to interview, the purpose of the study was elaborated clearly to the respondents before filling the questionnaire. One questionnaire was used for is each respondent for collection data. Researcher himself collected the date.

3.9. Data analysis: All collected data was checked and verified thoroughly to reduce the inconsistency. The data was edited, coded and entered into computer. Analysis was done according to the objective of the study using suitable statistical items of percentage. Results are presented in tables.

3.10. Work schedule:

Work schedule is shown in annexes.

CHAPTER-4 RESULTS

This cross sectional study was conducted among the adult people at Bara Uthan, Baralia, Bhatikan Unions of Patiya Upazilla in Chittagong District. The population size was about ten thousand. A representative sample of 206 respondents was calculated statistically. The major objective was to explore the knowledge & perception of hypertension among adult people in a selected rural area of Chattogram.

Table I: Distribution of the respondents by gender (n=206)

Gender	Number	Percent
Male	127	61.7
Female	79	38.3
Total	206	100.00

Table shows that percentage of male was 61.7 and percentage of female was 38.3. The mean age of the respondents were found 38.62 years and standard deviation 13.5.

Table- II: Distribution of the respondents by marital status (n =206)

Marital status	Number	Percent
Married	186	90.3
Unmarried	6	2.9
Widow / Widower	14	6.8
Total	206	100.0

The table shows that 186 of the respondents (93.3%) were married, 6 were unmarried (2.9%) and 14 were widow/widower (6.8%).

Table III: Distribution of the respondents by religion (n =206)

Religion	Number	Percent
Muslim	175	85
Hindu	31	15
Total	206	100

One hundred and seventy-five of the respondents (85%) were muslims and thirty-one were hindus (15%)

Table IV: Distribution of the respondents by knowledge about the relation of age with high BP (n= 206)

Age relation	Number	Percent
Related with age	148	71.8
Not related with age	36	17.5
Not known	22	10.7
Total	206	100

Shows 148 (71.8%) respondents mentioned that hypertension is related to age. 36 (17.5%) respondents said that there is no relationship between high BP and age. 22 (10.7%) respondents had no opinion about that. So 148 (71.8%) respondents had knowledge about relationship of hypertension with age.

Table- V: Distribution of the respondents by Smoking Habit (n= 206)

Smoking habit	Number	Percent
Smoker	70	34.0
Non Smoker	136	66.0
Total	206	100.0

The Table reveals that 70 (34%) respondents Were Smoker. 136 (66%) respondents were non smoker.

Table- VI: Distribution of the respondents by knowledge of complication of high BP (n=206)

Knowledge of consequences of high BP	Number	Percent
Unconscious	22	10.7
Paralysis	27	13.1
Stroke	68	33
Death	68	33
Not Known	43	20.9
Heart diseases	36	17.5
Total	264	128.2

- Multiple responses (though sample size is 206 but answer are 264 in number due to multiple answer.
- 58 respondents gave multiple answer, that means 58 (28.2%) respondents had knowledge about consequences of hypertension. 68 (33%) were found for each of stroke and death.

Table VII: Distribution of the respondents by number of family members (n=206)

No. of Family Members	Number	Percent
1	1	0.5
2	9	4.4
3	36	17.5
4	54	26.2
5	61	29.6
6	22	10.7
7	13	6.3
8	7	0.5
9	1	0.5
11	1	0.5
13	1	0.5
	206	100

The Number of Family member was one to thirteen. Maximum Family had five members. The mean value is found 4.66 mode is measured five and standard deviation is 1.6

Table VIII: Symptoms of Hypertension mentioned by the respondents (n=206)

Symptom of hypertension	Number	Percent
Palpitation	40	19.4
Excitation	9	4.3
Neck discomfort	103	50
Headache	99	48
Sweating	40	19.4
Vertigo	22	10.7
Nausea	15	7.3
Insomnia	16	7.8
Not known	5	7.2
Total	368	181

Multiple responses (Though sample size is 206 but answers are 368 in number due to multiple answers)

151 of the respondents gave multiple responses about symptom of hypertension. That means 151 (73.3%) respondents had knowledge about symptom of hypertension. 103 (50%) responses were neck discomfort, 99 (48%) responses were headache, 40 (19.4%) were palpitation in chest. Another 40 (19.4%) answers were sweating. 22

(10.7%) responds were vertigo, 19 (9.2%) responds were exhaustion. 15(7.3%) answers were nausea. 5 respondents were not known about the symptoms of hypertension. 9 (4.3%) answers were excitation as a symptom of hypertension. 16 (7.8%) respondents were insomnia.

Table IX: Distribution of the respondents by knowledge in relation to gender with high BP (n=206)

Gender relation	Number	Percent
Present	137	66.5
Absent	51	24.8
Not known	18	8.7
Total	206	100.0

137 (66.5%) respondents thought that gender is related to hypertension. 51 (24.8%) respondents gave their opinion that there is no relationship between hypertension and gender. So 137 (66.5%) respondents had knowledge about relationship of hypertension with gender. (Table11)

Table X: Distribution of the respondents by knowledge in relation to life style with high BP (n=206)

Relation of high BP with life style	Number	Percent
Present	174	84.5
Absent	7	3.4
Not known	25	12.1
Total	206	100.0

Table shows that 174 (84.5%) respondents mentioned that there is relationship between high BP and lifestyle. So, 174 (84.5%) respondents had knowledge about it. 7 (3.4%) respondents mentioned that there is no relationship between high BP and lifestyle. 25 (12.1%) respondents were not known about that relationship.

Table XI: Distribution of the respondents by knowledge in relation to food habit with high BP (n=206)

Relation of high BP with food habit	Number	Percent
Present	181	87.9
Absent	9	4.4
Not known	16	7.8
Total	206	100.0

Table reveals that 181 (87.9%) respondents thought that there is relationship between hypertension and food habit. So 181 (87.9%) respondents had knowledge about it. 9 (4.4%) respondents thought that there is no relationship between hypertension and food habit. 16 (7.8%) respondents were not known about that.

Table XII: Distribution of the respondents by knowledge of relation with diabetes and high BP (n=206)

relation with diabetes and high BP	Number	Percent
Present	44	21.4
Absent	86	41.7
Not Known	76	36.9
Total	206	100

Table reveals that 44 (21.4%) respondents had knowledge about it and mentioned that hypertension is related to diabetes. 86 (41.7%) respondents mentioned that hypertension is not related to diabetes.

Figure- I: Histogram showing Distribution of respondent by the Age

The result reveals that the number of population (15.5%) in 25 of less age group, (38.3%) in 26 to 35 age group, (21.8%) in 36 to 45 age group, (13.6%) in 46 to 55 age group, (10.7%) in 56 or above age group.

Figure II: Pie Chart Showing Distribution of respondents by occupation

The result reveals that population (39.3%) are housewife, (28.2%) are Cultivator, (16%) are Businessman, (7.8%) are Service holder, (5.8%) are Day labourer, (2.9%) are other respectively.

Figure III: Simple- Bar chart Showing Distribution of respondents by Educational Status

The Result reveals that (25.7%) respondents are illiterate, (31.6%) are class I-V, (27.2) are class VI to X, (15.5%) are H.S.C and above respectively.

CHAPTER- 5 DISCUSSION

This cross sectional study was conducted among the adult people at Patiya Upazilla in Chattogram District to assess the knowledge & perception of hypertension among adult people in a rural community of Bangladesh.

In this study sample size was determined by appropriate statistical method. Patiya was selected by purposive sampling. Patiya Upazilla has 22 Unions Sample was taken from 3 Unions The Three Unions were detected from the total 22 Unions by simple random sampling by lottery method. Two hundred and twenty (220) samples were taken from three unions by simple random sampling by lottery method. 14 people out of 220 were not found at the time of data collection, so collected sample size was 206. The total number of respondents was two hundred and six of which one hundred twenty-seven were male and seventy-nine were female. The percentage of male was 61.7 and percentage of female was 38.3.

The mean age of the respondents were found 38.62 years and standard deviation 13.5

148 (71.8%) respondents mentioned that hypertension is related to age.¹² 36 (17.5%) respondents said that there is no relationship between high BP and age. 22 (10.7%) respondents had no opinion about that. So 148 (71.8%) respondents had knowledge that hypertension is related to age. 68 (45.9%) respondents thought that the occurrence of hypertension is within the age group of 31 to 40 years. 52 (36%) respondents said that high BP occur within the age group of 41 to 50 years. 25 (16.8%) respondents gave their opinion that high BP occur 30 years or below age group. Major portion of the respondents know that hypertension is related to age but most of them had misconception about the age group in which hypertension occurs. It is also due to lack of education.

137 (66.5%) respondents mentioned that gender is related to hypertension. 51 (24.8%) respondents gave their opinion that there is no relationship between hypertension and gender.

103 (75.1%) respondents identified that males are at risk of hypertension. 34 (24.9%) respondents mentioned that females are at risk of hypertension. Most of the respondents (66.5%) know that hypertension is related to gender but some of them think males and others think females are at risk of hypertension. Such type of different conceptions is created by the respondents' personal experience. That means if a respondent observed more male hypertensive patients than female then the respondents would think that males are more prone to develop hypertension and vice versa.

174 (84.5%) respondents thought that there is relationship between high BP and lifestyle.¹³ 7 (3.4%) respondents thought that there is no relationship between high BP and lifestyle. 25 (12.1%) respondents were not known about that relationship.

181 (87.9%) respondents thought that there is relationship between hypertension and food habit. 9 (4.4%) respondents thought that there is relationship between hypertension and food habit. 16 (7.8%) respondents were not known about that.

162 (78.6%) respondents thought that obesity is related to hypertension. 34 (16.5%) respondents thought that there is no relationship between obese person and hypertension. 10 (4.9%) respondents did not know about that.

138 (67%) respondents had knowledge about relationship of hypertension with smoking because they mentioned that hypertension is related to smoking. 32 (15.5%) respondents thought that hypertension is not related to smoking. 36 (17.5%) respondents knew nothing about the relationship. 70 (34%) respondents were smoker. 136 (66%) respondents were non smoker. 31 out of 70 smokers gave their opinion that they would not give up smoking as they were habituated even after knowing that smoking may cause hypertension. This type of bad habit is enhanced by attractive advertisement.

97 (47.1%) respondents thought that hypertension might occur from parent. 59 (28.6%) respondents thought that hypertension not occur from parent. 50 (24.3%) respondents did not know anything about the relationship. This lack of knowledge (47.1%) may be due to less media coverage about hereditary relation of hypertension.

Only 44 (21.4%) respondents had knowledge about relationship of hypertension with diabetes because they thought that hypertension is related to diabetes. 86 (41.7%) respondents thought that hypertension is not related to diabetes. 76 (36.9%) respondents did not know anything about the relationship. Major portion of the respondents did not know the relation of hypertension with genetic factor and diabetes. This ignorance is due to lack of media coverage in that point.

Although most of the respondents gave their opinion about preventive measure of hypertension but the number of multiple responses were not satisfactory. This lacking is due improper use of mass media.

58 respondents gave multiple answers about complication of hypertension. That means only 58 (28.2%) respondents had knowledge about complication of hypertension. Most common answers about complication of hypertension were stroke and death. 68 (33%) responses were found for each of stroke and death. 43 (20.9%) responses expressed ignorance about the consequences of hypertension. 36 (17.5%) responses were indicated to heart disease. 27 (13.1%) responses were mentioned to paralysis. 22 (10.7%) answers were indicated to unconsciousness as a complication of hypertension. No significant relationship was found between educational status of the respondents and their knowledge about hypertension.

CHAPTER- 6

6.1 CONCLUSION

Hypertension in the rural areas of Bangladesh is increasing day by day. Now it is a public health problem in the rural areas of Bangladesh also. For the prevention of hypertension adequate knowledge about it is necessary to the people of the rural community.

- This study reveals that 73.3% respondents had knowledge about symptoms of hypertension but only 16 respondents out of 206, mentioned three symptoms of hypertension.
- 71.8% respondents mentioned that hypertension is related to age but most of them had no correct idea about the age group, which is prone to hypertension.
- 66.5% respondents thought that gender is related to hypertension but 103 respondents i.e total 50% respondents identified that males are at risk of hypertension.
- 181 (87.9%) respondents thought that there is relationship between hypertension and food habit but all of them failed to mention more than one food related to hypertension.
- 162 (78.6%) respondents thought that obese person is related to hypertension. 34 (16.5%) respondents thought that there is no relationship between obese person and hypertension.
- 170 (82.5%) respondents thought that hypertension is related to mental condition. 11 (5.3%) respondents thought that hypertension is not related to mental condition.
- 138 (67%) respondents mentioned that hypertension is related to smoking but 32 (15.5%) respondents thought that hypertension has no relation with smoking. 70 (34%) respondents were smoker. But 31 smokers would not give up smoking even after knowing that smoking might cause hypertension because they had created strong smoking habit.
- 97 (47.1%) respondents thought that hypertension might occur from parent. 59 (28.6%) respondents thought that hypertension not occur from parent.

- Only 44 (21.4%) respondents thought that hypertension is related to diabetes. 86 (41.7%) respondents thought that hypertension is not related to diabetes.
- Only 106 (51.5%) respondents had knowledge about prevention of hypertension, but 23 (11.2%) respondents gave incorrect answers.
- Only 58 (28.2%) respondents had knowledge about complication of hypertension.

6.2 LIMITATIONS OF THIS STUDY

The study had the following limitations:

- Limited access to information.
- Lack of previous studies in the research area.
- Unavailability of the respondents.
- Limited time.

6.3 RECOMMENDATION

Although the respondents of this study had some knowledge and perception of hypertension but this is not adequate to face hypertension as a public health problem. Following recommendations are made in the light of the results of the present study:

- A broad base study is needed to know the prevalence of hypertension in the rural areas of Bangladesh.
- Mass education is needed about hypertension for the rural people of Bangladesh.

CHAPTER-7

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Annexure-1

Work Plan

Activities	July 2021				August 2021				September 2021				October 2021				November 2021			
	Week				Week				Week				Week				Week			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Finalization to to topic																				
Planning & Design																				
Review of Literature																				
Preparation, questionnaire																				
Pre-testing, Questionnaire																				
Date collection																				
Data Analysis																				
Preliminary reporting																				
Collection of manuscript																				
Final print & submission																				

Questionnaire

Faculty of Science of School Health and Technology Bangladesh
Open University

I am a Researcher I want to ask you some questions for academic research purpose. The information, which will be given by you, will be used only for academic research purpose your information will be kept confidential. I hope you will help me by giving answers of the questions.

With thanks –

Dr. Sanjoy Kanti Nath
Course - MPH Session
2019-2020

Date

1. What is your name?
2. Where is your residence? Vill. Union-
PO. Upazilla- Dist
3. Sex (1) Male (2) Female
4. Age (In full years)
5. Marital status: (1) Married (2) Unmarried
 (3) Widower/Widow (4) Divorcee
6. Religion (1) Islam (2) Hindu
 (3) Christian (4) Buddhist
7. Occupation (1) Cultivator (2) Housewife
 (3) Service holder (4) Business
 (5) Day-labourer (6) Others (specify)
8. Educational qualification: (1) Illiterate (2) Class I to Class 5
 (3) Class 5 to Class 10 (4) Higher secondary and above
9. Number of family members.
10. What are the symptoms of high blood pressure?
 (1) Palpation (2) Excitation (3) Breathing difficulty
 (4) Pain in neck (5) Headache/ Pain in head (6) Sweating
 (7) Vertigo (8) Insomnia (9) Not known (10) Others (Specify)

11. Is high blood pressure related to age?

(1) Yes (2) No (3) Not known

(a) If yes, high blood pressure may occur in what age group?

12. Is high blood pressure related to sex?

(1) Yes (2) No (3) Not known

(a) If yes, which sex is more effected to high blood pressure?

(1) Male (2) Female

13. Is high blood pressure related to lifestyle?

(1) Yes (2) No (3) Not known

(a) If yes, which type of life style is related to blood pressure?

(1) Physical worker (2) Mental worker

14. Is high blood pressure related to food habit?

(1) Yes (2) No (3) Not known

(a) If yes, which type of food is related to blood pressure?

(1) Carbohydrate (2) Protein (3) Fat (4) Salt

(5) Others (Specify)

15. Is smoking one of the causes of high blood pressure?

(1) Yes (2) No (3) Not known

16. Do you smoke?

(1) Yes (2) No

If yes, do you like to continue smoking after knowing the fact that smoking causes high blood pressure?

(a) (1) Yes (2) No

(b) If yes, what is the your logic?

17. Is there any chance of developing high blood pressure of the children when the parents are hypertensive?

(1) Yes (2) No (3) Not known

18. Is high blood pressure related to diabetes?

(1) Yes (2) No (3) Not known

19. What are the consequences of high blood pressure?

(1) Unconsciousness (2) Paralysis (3) Stroke (4) Death

(5) Not known (6) Others (Specify)

Signature of the respondent

Signature of the researcher

প্রশ্নমালা

আমি একজন গবেষক। গবেষণার প্রয়োজনে আমি আপনাকে কিছু প্রশ্ন করতে চাই। আপনার দেয়া সমস্ত তথ্য গোপন হবে এবং শিক্ষাকোর্সে অন্তর্ভুক্ত রিপোর্ট তৈরীর প্রয়োজনে শুধুমাত্র পরিসংখ্যানগত সাধারণ তথ্য সমূহ (ব্যক্তিগত নয়) ব্যবহার করা হবে। আশা করি আপনি প্রশ্ন সমূহের উত্তর দিয়ে আমাকে সহায়তা করবেন।

ধন্যবাদান্তে-

ডাঃ সঞ্জয় কান্তি নাথ

এম.পি. এইচ শিক্ষার্থী

তারিখ:

- ১। নাম:
- ২। ঠিকানা:
গ্রাম- ইউনিয়ন- পোঃ-
উপজেলা- জেলা-
- ৩। লিঙ্গ: (১) পুরুষ (২) মহিলা
- ৪। বয়স: (পূর্ণ বয়সে)
- ৫। বৈবাহিক অবস্থা: (১) বিবাহিত (২) (অবিবাহিত)
(৩) বিপত্নীক/বিধবা (৪) তালাকপ্রাপ্ত
- ৬। ধর্ম: (১) ইসলাম (২) হিন্দু
(৩) খৃষ্টান (৪) বৌদ্ধ
- ৭। জীবিকা: (১) কৃষিজীবী (২) গৃহস্থ
(৩) চাকুরীজীবী (৪) ব্যকসা
(৫) দিনমজুর (৬) অন্যান্য (নির্দিষ্ট করুন)
- ৮। শিক্ষাগত যোগ্যতা: (১) নিরক্ষর (২) ১ম থেকে ৫ম শ্রেণী
(৩) ষষ্ঠ থেকে দশম শ্রেণী (৪) উচ্চ মাধ্যমিক ও তদুর্ধ
- ৯। পরিবারের সদস্য সংখ্যা:
- ১০। কি কি লক্ষণের মাধ্যমে উচ্চ রক্তচাপ বোঝা যায়?
(১) বুক ধড়ফড় (২) উত্তেজিত হওয়া (৩) হাঁপাতে থাকা
(৪) ঘাড়ে ব্যথা হওয়া (৫) মাথা ব্যথা হওয়া (৬) ঘাম হওয়া
(৭) মাথা ঘোরা (৮) ঘুম কম হওয়া (৯) জানা নাই
(১০) অন্যান্য (নির্দিষ্ট করুন)
- ১১। উচ্চ রক্তচাপ কি বয়সের সাথে সম্পর্কযুক্ত?
(১) হ্যাঁ (২) না (৩) জানা নাই
ক) হ্যাঁ হলে, কোন বয়সে উচ্চ রক্তচাপ হতে পারে?
- ১২। উচ্চ রক্তচাপের সঙ্গে লিঙ্গের কোন পার্থক্য আছে?
(১) হ্যাঁ (২) না (৩) জানা নাই
ক) হ্যাঁ হলে, কোন লিঙ্গের উচ্চ রক্তচাপ বেশী হয়?
(১) পুরুষ (২) মহিলা
- ১৩। জীবনধারণের সঙ্গে উচ্চ রক্তচাপের সম্পর্ক আছে কি?

- (১) হ্যাঁ (২) না (৩) জানা নাই
- (ক) হ্যাঁ হলে, কোন ধরনের জীবনধারা উচ্চ রক্তচাপের সাথে সম্পর্কযুক্ত?
- (১) শারিরিক শ্রমজীবী (২) মানসিক শ্রমজীবী
- ১৪। খাদ্যাভ্যাসের সঙ্গে উচ্চ চাপের সম্পর্ক আছে কি?
- (১) হ্যাঁ (২) না (৩) জানা নাই
- (ক) হ্যাঁ হলে, কোন ধরনের মান্য উচ্চ রক্তচাপের সঙ্গে সম্পর্কযুক্ত?
- (১) শর্করা (২) আমিষ (৩) স্নেহ জাতীয় খাদ্য (৪) লবণ
- (৫) অন্যান্য (নির্দিষ্ট করুন)
- ১৫। ধূমপান কি উচ্চ রক্তচাপের অন্যতম কারণ?
- (১) হ্যাঁ (২) না
- ১৬। আপনি ধূমপান করেন কি?
- (১) হ্যাঁ (২) না
- (ক) হ্যাঁ হলে, ধূমপান উচ্চ রক্তচাপ সৃষ্টি করতে পারে এটা জানলেও কি আপনি ধূমপান চালিয়ে যেতে চান?
- (১) হ্যাঁ (২) না
- (ক) হ্যাঁ হলে, আপনার স্বপক্ষে যুক্তি কি?
- ১৭। বাবা/মায়ের উচ্চ রক্তচাপ থাকলে সন্তানের উচ্চ রক্তচাপ হওয়ার সম্ভাবনা আছে কি?
- (১) হ্যাঁ (২) না (৩) জানা নাই
- ১৮। উচ্চ রক্তচাপের সঙ্গে ডায়াবেটিসের (বহুমূত্র রোগ) সম্পর্ক আছে কি?
- (১) হ্যাঁ (২) না (৩) জানা নাই
- ১৯। উচ্চ রক্তচাপের কি কি ফল হতে পারে?
- (১) অচেতন হওয়া (২) পারালাইসিস হওয়া (৩) স্ট্রোক হওয়া (৪) মৃত্যু
- (৫) জানা নাই (৬) অন্যান্য (নির্দিষ্ট করুন)

উত্তরদাতার স্বাক্ষর

গবেষকের স্বাক্ষর

